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COVER ART – The cover art was painted by Jason Poole and depicts a school of Mosasaurs.

AN EARLY SILURIAN FISH FROM THE CLINCH (TUSCARORA) SANDSTONE OF VIRGINIA

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ABSTRACT – A fossil fish bone is reported from the Early Silurian Clinch (Tuscarora) Sandstone of Lee County, southwestern Virginia. This Silurian fish specimen constitutes the oldest occurrence of fossil fish yet found in eastern North America, which then lay along the margin of the Taconic land mass. Fish remains of early Silurian age were reported by Lyell from western Virginia over one hundred and fifty years ago, but the validity of his observation has been disputed until now.

INTRODUCTION AND GEOLOGIC SETTING

Upper Silurian fish remains have been intermittently reported from the Appalachian region (Figure 1) for well over one hundred and fifty years (Lyell, 1842). The earliest well documented fish remains from this region (the cyathaspids *Americaspis* and *Vernonaspis*) came from the Late Silurian Wills Creek Formation in New York, New Jersey, Pennsylvania, Maryland, and West Virginia (Leutze, 1960; Denison, 1964). Somewhat later, an occurrence of thelodontian fish remains (*Logania* and *Thelodus*) was reported from the Late Silurian Bloomsburg Formation of Pennsylvania (Giffin, 1979). Because there has been no reliable evidence of Early Silurian fish

from the Appalachian region, it is of considerable interest to report here the discovery of a fossil fish bone in the Early Silurian of southwestern Virginia. This specimen comes from the Lower Silurian Clinch (Tuscarora) Sandstone in the Powell Valley, just to the west of the eastern boundary of Lee County, Virginia. There, a bone of a Paleozoic fish was found within a quartzite block that came from the lowest level of what has there been called the Clinch Formation (Bates, 1939). In southwestern Virginia, this unit is considered to be of shallow marine origin (Dorsch and Driese, 1993). The detailed taxonomic assignment of the single specimen so far found is discussed below.

Figure 1 – Locations where Silurian fossil fish have been described in and near the Appalachian Mountains region of the eastern United States. Localities are described in Leutze, 1960 (L), Denison, 1964 (D), and Giffin, 1979 (G). The unlabeled locality in southwestern Virginia is the one described herein. Dashed and dotted line marks the margins of the modern Appalachian Mountains and Cumberland Plateau regions of the eastern United States.

INSTITUTIONAL ABBREVIATION

VMNH. Virginia Museum of Natural History, Martinsville, Virginia.

SYSTEMATIC DESCRIPTION

Phylum Chordata Haeckel, 1874

Subphylum Vertebrata J.B.M. de Lamarck, 1801

Infraphylum Agnatha Cope, 1889

Class Osteostraci Lankester, 1868

Order Thyestiida Janvier, 1996

Family Tremataspidae Woodward, 1891

Genus *Tremataspis* Schmidt, 1866

aff. Tremataspis sp.

Figured Specimen — Dermoskeletal tessera (VMNH 129498) found by Gary J. Grimsley and Robert E. Weems.

Locality — Locality details are kept with the specimen at the Virginia Museum of Natural History (VMNH). It was found in the eastern part of Powell Valley, to the west of the eastern boundary of Lee County, Virginia.

Stratigraphic Unit and Age — This fossil was found near the base of the Clinch Sandstone (= Tuscarora Sandstone), which is of Early Silurian

age (Boucot et al., 1994). The Clinch Sandstone formed in a shallow marine depositional environment (Dorsch and Driese, 1993), so in all likelihood this fossil represents a shallow marine fish.

Discussion — The element illustrated here (Figure 2) appears to be a dermoskeletal tessera of an osteostracine fish that was located near its sub oral region (Figure 3). The edges of the preserved element are rather rounded and polished, which is interpreted to represent slight rounding of the bone by current or surf immediately prior to its burial. This osteoderm shows no indication that it possessed a shingled structure like that present in scales from the body armor region. Exceptionally for an osteostracine fish, this bone has a pock-marked or honeycombed pattern on its external surface that is similar to that found on some head-shield elements of *Tremataspis* (e.g., Afanassieva, 2004, Figures 1 B, C), though *Tremataspis* specimens from its type area also have deep pits scattered about on the surface of some of its bony elements that are not present in the specimen reported here. As *Tremataspis* has been reported only from the Upper Silurian of Estonia, and so is distant in time and space from the basal Silurian of Virginia, the specimen illustrated here is only tentatively associated with *Tremataspis*. If more complete remains of this fish are found, it may well prove to be a new and previously unidentified taxon.

Figure 2 – Photograph of a dermoskeletal tessera (VMNH 129498, aff. *Tremataspis* sp.) found in the Clinch (Tuscarora) Sandstone in southwestern Virginia in (A) external, (B) internal, and (C) lateral views.

Tremataspis mammillata

Figure 3 – Reconstruction of the life appearance of *Tremataspis mammillata*, known from the Upper Silurian of Estonia (after Janvier, 1985). The sub oral region is covered by a large number of small osteodermal elements similar to the one described here.

DISCUSSION

The early fossil vertebrate literature for Virginia included a report of fossil fish remains from the "Clinton group" in southwestern Virginia, which lies directly above the Clinch (Tuscarora) Sandstone (Swartz, 1923; Whisonant, 1977). In that report, Lyell (1842, vol. 2, p. 48-49) stated that: "In England, the remains of fish have long been known in the highest beds of the Upper Silurian, and they have lately been found as far down as the Wenlock limestone. The New York surveyors have met with them in more than one member of the Helderberg series.... But the lowest rock in which they have been traced in America is, I believe, the Clinton group, which may be considered the bottom of the Upper, or top of the Lower, Silurian series. Mr. H. D. Rogers informs me, that he and his brother have traced the scales of fish through strata of this series from the south-western part of Virginia to the north branch of the Susquehanna, in Pennsylvania". Claypole (1885, p. 60), citing this reference, pointed out that the literature published by H. D. Rogers failed to include any mention of fossil fish in Virginia from any rocks older than the Upper Devonian. For this reason he cast doubt on the validity of this report of early fossil fish in Virginia and, since that time, Lyell's report of fish in the Lower Silurian "Clinton group" apparently has been forgotten.

The discovery of fish remains in the Clinch (Tuscarora) Sandstone in southwestern Virginia may validate Lyell's 1842 report, which was based on an unpublished observation of H. D. Rogers that Silurian

fish remains do occur within the "Clinton group" in southwestern Virginia. This is only probably true, however, because Lyell in 1842 would not have distinguished the Clinton Group (named by Vanuxem in 1839) from the "Clinch Mountain Sandstone" (Safford, 1856) or "Tuscarora Quartzite" (Darton and Taff, 1896), neither of which was formally named until much later. Therefore, Lyell (1842) may well have included the Clinch and Tuscarora sandstones in what he called the "Clinton group," but this is not determinable with certainty at present. In any case, the presently reported occurrence of fossil fish in the Clinch (Tuscarora) Sandstone of southwestern Virginia likely vindicates Lyell's report and, even if it does not, definitely constitutes the oldest documentable occurrence of fossil fish in the Appalachian region of eastern North America.

To date, the only older reports of fossil fish from anywhere in North America are from the Middle to Late Ordovician mid-continent region, specifically in the Harding Sandstone in Colorado and Wyoming, the Whitewood Formation in South Dakota, the Arbuckle Mountains in Oklahoma, the Gull River Formation in Ontario, Canada, and the Black River Group in Quebec, Canada (Sansom et al., 1997). All of these occurrences are in deposits that accumulated during the Ordovician in the shallow epicontinental sea that then spread across North America to the west of the deeper water Appalachian seaway. It remains uncertain if these Ordovician occurrences of fossil fish from North America are all restricted to the shallow seas that were then present west of the

Appalachians, or whether fish remains may yet be found in some of the shallower water units that were intermittently present in the Appalachian region during late Ordovician time.

This specimen of an osteostracine fish is older than most other specimens so far described in the literature. There is only one other specimen from Estonia (*Kalanaspis delectabilis*), known from a head shield, that is just about as old in its occurrence as the specimen described here (Tinn and Märss, 2018). It is entirely possible that the uplift of the Taconic highlands on the eastern border of Appalachia at the beginning of the Silurian was the reason why osteostracine fishes co-existed in both regions at that time.

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